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NUMERICAL STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES INFLUENCING BALLISTIC IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN FABRICS USING CONSTANT TOUGHNESS APPROACH.

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Contents

- Introduction.
- Woven fabrics.
- Need of study.
- Types of geometric models.
- Parametric Study.
- Conclusion.

Introduction.

Pre world war period :

- Armours were heavy .
- Less protection against stab and bullet penetration.

During world war :

- Development of alloy and ceramics.
- Armours were heavy and less flexible.

Post world war period:

- Metal-composite armours.
- Relatively less weight and lacking flexibility.

Current trend:

- Dry woven fabric and composite armours.
- STF impregnated armours.
- Low weight ,high strength and highly flexible
e.g. *Kevlar ,Spectra, Zylon ,Twaron ,Dyneema*

Woven Fabrics

Woven fabrics are woven flexible structures made up warp and weft yarns which are interlaced orthogonally.

They have:

- High strength to weight ratio.
- Low density
- High toughness
- Flexible

Application: Ballistic Armours.

Factors influencing energy absorption of woven fabric:

Toughness of yarn:

- Young's Modulus of Yarn.
- Strength of Yarn.
- Failure strain of yarn

Friction:

- Interyarn Friction (Friction between Warp and Weft yarn)
- Interlayer Friction
- Friction between projectile and fabric.

Boundary conditions:

- Fixed-fixed
- Fixed-free

Need of Study:

- Till date parametric study on influence of material properties on ballistic performance was done by changing one material property and keeping others constant.
- This resulted in change in toughness of material.
- More realistic approach was needed to find out best combination of material properties for enhanced ballistic performance.
- Very few literature has been reported on interlayer Coefficient of friction (COF) effects on ballistic performance.

Geometric Models.

- Macroscopic Model
- Mesoscopic Model

Macroscopic Model:

- Macroscopic model is fabric level model.
- Fabric is modelled as transversely isotropic homogenous thin plate.
- Does not include inter yarn friction effects.
- Generally used in :
 - Parametric studies related to properties.
 - Interlayer friction studies.
 - Model large structures.
- Saves lot of computation time.

Mesoscopic Model:

- Yarn level model.
- Yarn is modelled Using parametric equation of curve.
- Yarn to yarn friction interaction can be modelled.
- High computational time.

Study 1: Energy absorption analysis using constant toughness approach.

Numerical modelling Details:

- Macroscopic model.
- Frictionless contacts.
- Fixed-fixed boundary condition.
- Shell element used.
- Toughness of material constant.
- Base material 2 (Kevlar km2)

Material Properties:

Material	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3
Longitudinal Modulus (GPa)	16.3	65.5	262
Failure Strain (%)	11	5.5	2.75
Failure Stress (GPa)	1.8	3.6	7.2
Toughness (GPa/vol)	99	99	99

Results:

Table: Residual Velocity of projectile for different materials.

Striking Velocity	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3
	Residual velocity of projectile		
175	4	103	132
200	10	158	165
250	178	222	236
300	255	278	288
350	323	336	339
400	377	384	389
600	590	591	592
700	689	690	691
800	788	788	790

Plot 1: Residual Velocity Vs. Striking Velocity

- Mat 1 with Low longitudinal modulus and High failure strain absorbs maximum energy.
- while Mat 3 with high longitudinal modulus and low failure strain absorbs minimum energy for all range of Velocities.

Table : Percentage of Energy absorption for materials.

Striking Velocity	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat3
	Percentage of Energy absorbed by fabric.		
175	99.94	65.38	43.1
200	99.75	37.6	31.93
250	49.3	21.14	10.88
300	27.75	14.12	7.84
350	14.83	7.84	6.18
400	11.16	7.84	5.42
600	3.3	2.97	2.64
700	3.11	2.83	2.55
800	2.97	2.97	2.48

Plot 2: Striking velocity vs. Percentage of projectile energy absorbed

- Percentage of Energy absorption for all three materials decreases with increasing striking velocities.
- At high velocities difference in energy absorbed by materials is very less, this implies that at high velocities variation in material properties does not influence energy absorption.

Fig :Formation of deformation cone.

- Diameter of deformation cone formed just before failure is very large in Mat 1 compared to other two materials.
- Implies that transverse wave has travelled more distance from impact centre in case of Mat 1 which results in more area of fabric taking part in energy absorption thus resulting in maximum energy absorption as well as high Ballistic limit velocity (BLV)

	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3
BLV	155	132	82

Study 2 : Comparative study on energy absorption of woven fabrics.

Material modelling:

- Single layer macroscopic model.
- Friction less contacts.
- Materials are normalized on weights.
- Shell element

Material Properties:

	Kevlar KM2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon AS	Twaron
Young's Modulus (Gpa)	84.62	70.5	171	180	110
σ_{\max} (GPa)	3.9	3.6	3	5.8	3
$\epsilon_{\text{failure}}$ (%)	4.58	5.5	1.8	3.2	2.6
Density (kg/m3)	1440	1440	970	1540	1450

Results:

Striking velocity	Kevlar km2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon	Twaron
Residual velocity of projectile					
125	28	10	102	72	103
150	107	48	131	117	133
175	143	122	157	147	167
200	173	162	184	178	193
225	202	193	210	199	218
250	237	225	237	228	243
275	263	255	262	263	269
300	289	284	287	291	293
325	314	310	313	315	319
350	339	337	338	341	343
375	365	363	364	367	369
Ballistic Limit Velocity	101	112	60	90	54

- Material with low modulus and high failure strain absorbs maximum energy (evident by constant toughness approach).
- For all range of velocities Kevlar 29 absorbs maximum energy and Twaron absorbs minimum.

Results:

- Energy absorbing capacity of all woven fabric decreases with increasing striking velocity.
- Difference in energy absorbed between Kevlar 29 and Twaron decreases significantly.
- Nature of % decrease in energy absorbed is negative exponential

Results:

	Toughness (MPa/Vol)	BLV (m/s)	Failure time(μs)
Kevlar km2	89	101	52.5
Kevlar 29	99	112	65
Spectra 1000	27	60	55
Zylon	92.8	90	47.5
Twaron	39	54	35

- Results reveal that only high toughness is not sufficient condition for high BLV, it should have low toughness and high failure strain value.
- Zylon has high toughness compared to Kevlar km2 but BLV for Kevlar km2 is more cause it has low modulus and high failure strain.
- Hence it is proved by constant toughness approach that low modulus and high failure strain are favourable condition for maximum energy absorption.

Study 3: Effect of Interlayer COF on Energy absorption of different woven fabrics

Numerical Modelling:

- 8 layer macroscopic level model.
- Two edge fix-two free.
- Shell element used.
- Frictionless contact between projectile and fabric.

COF	Kevlar km2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon	Twaron
Residual Velocity					
0	257	254	300	265	307
0.1	250	242	295	256	304
0.2	248	235	296	250	306
0.3	244	230	302	250	306
0.4	235	230	303	246	306
0.5	239	228	304	249	305
0.6	244	231	305	249	305
0.7	249	231	305	248	305
0.8	250	233	305	250	306
0.9	250	236	306	250	306
0.99	250	236	306	251	306

- All the woven fabrics shows increase in energy absorption with increase in COF up to certain value after that energy absorption decreases and remain constant
- Threshold values:

Material	Kevlar km2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon	Twaron
Threshold COF	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.1

- Above results show that, materials with high value of toughness, we can afford to increase COF to increase energy absorption.
- With increase in COF after threshold value localized tensile stress starts increasing, which helps in damaging fabric and results in failure.

Conclusions:

- Low longitudinal modulus and high failure strain is best combination for maximum energy absorption.
- High longitudinal modulus and low failure strain results in minimum energy absorption.
- Results reveal that only high toughness is not sufficient condition for high BLV, it should have low toughness and high failure strain value.
- Energy absorption of material decreases as projectile striking velocity decreases.
- At high velocities variation in material properties does not influence energy absorption.
- All the woven fabrics shows increase in energy absorption with increase in COF up to certain value after that energy absorption decreases and remain constant.
- Materials with high value of toughness, we can afford to increase COF to increase energy absorption.

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